

PAKISTAN GOVERNMENT & TRIBAL CHIEFS OF BALOCHISTAN: AN ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The restive province of Balochistan constitutes the biggest domestic threat to the very existence of Pakistan. Baloch nationalists have accused the federal government that in spite of the fact that it has exploited the natural resources of the province to the hilt, nothing has been done for the development of this region. The anger of the nationalists has resulted in four unsuccessful insurgencies against the federal government in the past 62 years. The latest Baloch uprising may even jeopardize the war on terror. The government contends that the Baloch Sardars (tribal chiefs) are the biggest hindrance in the path of peace and prosperity in the province because the Sardars fear that education and economic development will erode their traditional authority over a tribal society. This paper explores the question whether the root cause of the Balochistan problem is the conflict between the traditional authority of the Sardars and the modern authority of the state. This paper argues that while the role of the Jirgas (traditional councils) and Sardars may be questionable in perpetuating of social evils like violence against women, the conflict per se is not due to the obstinacy of the tribal chiefs. The conflict has been deliberately framed by the government as a war between tradition and modernity. The real solution to the problem lies in offering Balochistan a greater share of the economic bounty that the province provides to the country as well as in assuring an insecure populace that the government has no intention of manipulating the demographic composition of their region. While Musharraf's high-handed handling of the region had exacerbated the problem, the current Pakistan People's Party led federal government has a unique opportunity, since the same party is in power in the province also, to resolve the Balochistan conundrum that has plagued Pakistan from its very inception.

Keywords: Balochistan, Tribal, Terror

Introduction

Although, the Asif Ail Zardari led Pakistan People's Party government has offered an olive branch to Baloch nationalists, the conflict continues unabated, albeit with less intensity, as the insurgent groups have called off the ceasefire from January 1, 2009. Attacks on army personnel, the murder of Punjabi immigrants and the frequent strikes on gas pipelines have ensured that even if the crisis may not be as severe as it was during the Musharraf regime, but it could still escalate to that level in no time given the slightest provocation. Since this paper proposes to understand the Balochistan conundrum from the prism of the conflict between traditional and modern authority, it is prudent to establish theoretical benchmarks first.

Why Balochistan Matters?

Balochistan, which borders the Arabian Sea, Afghanistan and Iran, is a vast and sparsely populated province. It occupies 42 per cent of Pakistan's geographical area but only five per cent of the country's population lives there. Economically as well as strategically, Balochistan is without doubt the most important province of Pakistan. Over a quarter of a century ago, Harrison observed, "If it were not for the strategic location of Balochistan and the rich potential of oil, uranium and other resources, it would be difficult to imagine anyone fighting over this bleak, desolate, and forbidding land"(Harrison 1981, 1). Since then, with every passing year, Balochistan's strategic and economic importance has shot up ever higher. As a matter of fact, it is now considered to be crucial for Pakistan's energy security. Balochistan has significant reserves of coal and natural gas, and it may hold large reserves of petroleum also. However, it is the reserves of natural gas that make Balochistan the backbone of Pakistan's energy profile. In 2006, Pakistan's total gas reserves were estimated at 28 trillion cubic feet (tcf). Of this, 19 tcf (68 per cent) are located within Balochistan. Balochistan accounts for 36 to 45 per cent of Pakistan's production of natural gas but consumes only 17 per cent of it. The largest share of Balochistan's contribution to Pakistan's natural gas production comes from Sui gas fields in the Bugti tribal domain, located among those parts, which are most seriously affected by Baloch insurgency. Apart from this, two ambitious multinational projects for transporting natural gas via overland pipelines, passing through Balochistan, to markets in India and Pakistan are being actively considered (Wirsing 2008, 15, 18). Also, exploration work has already begun on what has been described as probably the world's largest gold and copper reserves in Reko Dik area in the Chagai district of Balochistan. Beijing already operates gold and copper mines in Saindak, near the borders of Afghanistan and Iran.

For understanding the strategic importance of the province one needs to remember that a significant number of Baloch people are spread over parts of Iran and Afghanistan also. Insurgent groups, demanding a greater Balochistan,

claim these areas of Iran and Afghanistan as well. However, Pakistan's Balochistan is bordered internationally by the Arabian Sea in the south, by Iran in the west and by Afghanistan to the north. In recent years, it has acquired geostrategic importance for the US, China, India, and Iran. Balochistan is an important theater in the US led war on terror. A large part of the US military operations are launched from the Pasni and Dalbandin bases located in this province (Grare 2006,6). Shamsi airfield, in Southern Balochistan, is being secretly used by the US intelligence agencies to mount Predator drone attacks on Al-Qaeda and Taliban hideouts on the Pak-Afghan border. The strip is just 50 km. from the Afghan border and allows the US forces to carry out strategic surveillance of the entire stretch of the Pak-Afghan border, from the Bolan pass in Balochistan to Parachinar in Kurram agency in NWFP (The Hindu 2009). Taliban and Al-Qaeda also have a strong presence in Balochistan. It is widely speculated that the US might even support Baloch nationalists in order to defeat Pashtun Taliban. If the US ever launches military strikes on Iran, airports of Pasni, Gwadar, Turbak, Juzzak and Robray will be of crucial strategic importance.

Pakistan's construction of a Chinese-funded port in the Baloch town of Gwadar has added a new dimension to the regional geopolitics, with the port attracting the interest of the militaries of Pakistan's powerful neighbors, especially India and Iran. With the deployment of U.S. troops in Afghanistan since 2001, China too has shown an enhanced interest in the region, indeed expediting the construction of the Gwadar Port. When the port was declared "fully functional" on December 21, 2008, a report by the Associated Press of Pakistan, a government-run news agency, highlighted its strategic significance, noting: "Gwadar will serve as an energy corridor for Central Asia, the Middle East, South Asia and the western part of Asia. The significance of Gwadar is great to both Pakistan and China. Pakistan will be able to have a strategic depth southwest from its naval base in Karachi." The Chinese investment in the multi-billion dollar project worries India, as it will erode the Indian Navy's dominance over the Indian Ocean. India has been often accused by Pakistani leaders of fomenting the Baloch insurgency. The port is located at the mouth of the Persian Gulf through which nearly 30 percent of the world's oil supplies pass. Like India, Iran too views it as a threat to its security and economic dominance in the region (Ahmad 2009). Gwadar port has been designed to bolster Pakistan's strategic defense by providing an alternative to the port of Karachi, which had to face a long blockade by the Indian navy during the war of 1971. Karachi's vulnerability was confirmed when another blockade loomed large during the Kargil conflict in 1999. The construction of the Omara base in Balochistan, which became operational in 2000, is also a part of the same policy. A listening post on the Makaran Coast of Balochistan may have been set up by China to intercept the communication of the US military in the Gulf (Grare 2006, 7).

Balochistan is also the main base for the space program and rocket experimentation facilities of Pakistan. And last but most certainly not the least, Pakistan's nuclear explosions of 1998 took place in the Chaghai hills of the province. Moreover, Balochistan is the only tract that promises extraction of Uranium to quench Pakistan's thirst for weapons grade fissile material (Dhar 2007).

The verdict of the Jirga is still the strongest force in the tribal society. The force behind the Jirga is the age-old conventions, traditions and ethics of the tribal society. According to tribal ethics, any attempt to tamper with one's loyalty is no less a crime than touching the honor of a woman. The traditional penalty for both is summary death (Participatory Development Initiatives 2005, 17-18). One cannot ignore the fact that the Jirga system has been responsible for some of the worst human rights violations in the world. And indeed, some of the Sardars have justified these violations by arguing that these practices are part of age-old Baloch traditions. For instance, in June 2008, three teenage girls who planned to defy their parents and marry the men of their choice were buried alive as honor killings. The accused was a younger brother of a minister in Balochistan's provincial government and the police did its best to protect him (Hussain 2008). Apart from these kinds of incidents, it is a usual practice in Balochistan that Jirgas ask alleged criminals to walk on burning coal to prove their innocence. Sadly, after two such cases were reported in January 2009, the Minister for Human Rights in the Balochistan government remarked that these practices were a part of the local tradition and no one, including the government, could eliminate them (Akbar 2009). The Pakistani government uses these condemnable practices to portray the Sardari-Jirga system as barbaric and to justify its hard-hitting actions.

It can be concluded that the system of Jirga was initiated by Naseer Khan for involving tribes in administration. In this system the role of the Sardar was of far less importance. But with the advent of the British the role of the Sardar became almost like a feudal lord. Now these Sardars are leading their tribes in Baloch insurgency. In order to comprehend how the traditional authority of the Sardars intersects with the modern authority of the Pakistani state, it becomes necessary to first underscore the structural imbalance of Pakistan.

The question of 'disappeared persons' is another issue that generated immense hatred among the Baloch nationalists towards the state security agencies. At the height of insurgency during the Musharraf regime, hundreds of persons including women were picked up by security agencies and since then they have never been heard of again. These persons were never produced in court and the government says that they are not in jail. In February 2009, the kidnappers of John Solecki, chief of UNHCR in Pakistan, demanded the release of these disappeared persons. Before becoming the President, Zardari had

promised to release these persons (Hyat 2009). But in the wake of the Solecki kidnapping, Rehman Malik, advisor to the Prime Minister, callously remarked that the number of missing persons is actually far less than usually claimed and that most of the supposedly 'missing persons are undergoing training in Afghanistan to perpetrate terrorism' (Malik 2009).

As pointed out earlier, although the Zardari government is doing its best to address the concerns of the Baloch nationalists, one cannot ignore the fact that the civilian government is subservient to the omnipotent Army in Pakistan. Wirsing contends that the Army has a three-pronged strategy of conflict management in Balochistan. As part of political management, the Army adopts the strategy of harassing, intimidating and occasionally decapitating Baloch leadership apart from using the tactics of divide and rule and the co-option of malleable tribal chiefs. As military management, 'you won't know what hit you' kinds of threats are employed and insurgents are ruthlessly suppressed. Increased deployment of security forces and the construction of military roads and cantonments are also part of it. As part of information management the ruling establishment has a time-tested strategy of demonizing Baloch Sardars to argue that insurgency in the province is a result of the barbaric feudal chiefs' desire to oppose development, in order to protect their traditional stranglehold over an illiterate and pliant tribal populace. The remarks of tribal chiefs such as 'can live with a pig but can't with a Punjabi' help the military's agenda further.

Resolving the Conundrum

Result of this study favor the logic of pragmatic traditionalists. The interactions between traditional and modern authority does not necessarily have to be antagonistic. Pakistani state has deliberately framed the conflict as one between traditional and modern authority in order to justify its ruthless suppression of Baloch nationalists. It is high time when Pakistan should realize that Baloch Sardars are there and they cannot be wished away. Considering the historical facts objectively, it can be concluded that the demands of Baloch nationalists are genuine. The Army and the ruling establishment have treated Balochistan as a colony to expropriate the massive wealth of the province. Although tribal practices such as honor killings and walking on fire to prove one's innocence are condemnable, they cannot be used to portray the entire Baloch society as barbaric and uncivilized, especially since such practices are somewhat common in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India and in the rest of Pakistan. Sardars do have a strong hold over Baloch people but it is due to tribal culture and this hold per se does not automatically brand them as undemocratic. One cannot forget that the Sardars of all major tribes such as Bugti, Mengal and Marri have contested elections and held posts of Chief Ministers and Governors in the province. Western intelligentsia should keep in mind the fact that the nature of South Asian political culture is different than that of the west. For instance, in India,

touted as the biggest democracy in the world, royals usually contest elections, win with hefty majorities and hold posts of Chief Ministers in the states. There is nothing inherently undemocratic, therefore, about Sardars winning elections and becoming Chief Ministers and Governors in Balochistan. As far as the greed of the Sardars is concerned, had they been insatiably hungry for money they would have preferred to be co-opted by the federal government rather than taking to treacherous terrains for the waging of unsuccessful insurgencies and getting killed. This should be kept in mind that the government was always willing to co-opt Sardars and offer them hefty rewards. On the contrary, it is the Army that as a corporate player has become a moneymaking entity and therefore does not want to relinquish the colossal wealth of Balochistan. Time and again it has been proved that the Pakistani government has tremendous resources and the tenacity to crush insurgency in Balochistan. In spite of this, Sardars are fighting and so it proves that they feel duty-bound by the tribal code of honor. Silver lining is that it is still not too late. All the indications are that the demand for independence is merely a negotiating stance and Baloch nationalists would be satisfied if they are offered increased autonomy, control over their natural resources and participation in managing the mega-projects like Gwadar. Population should not be the sole criterion for the distribution of revenues between center and provinces. The land area, backwardness of the people and the contribution of natural resources should also be considered, in which case the lion's share of Punjab in revenues can be reduced and Balochistan may have access to adequate funds for its developmental needs. The government should also come clean on the issue of 'disappeared persons'. Even if they have been killed by security agencies, the government should apologize, punish the guilty and move ahead on the path of rapprochement. Exigencies imposed by energy security and the fact that PPP led government is in power in the both restive province and center, have opened a unique window of opportunity for resolving the Balochistan conundrum. But for this to happen the unnatural importance of Punjab and Army in Pakistan's polity has to diminish and ruling elite has to show a genuine spirit of federalism. There is no need to tame, but to accommodate Baloch Sardars so they could become the engines of peace and prosperity.

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